

2. Великий тлумачний словник сучасної української мови: 250000. /уклад. та голов. ред. В. Т. Бусел. Київ; Ірпінь: Перун, 2005. 1728 с.
3. Мелешко Л. В. Формування мовленнєвої компетентності учнів 5-6 класів в ігровій діяльності на уроках української мови.: дис. ... канд. пед. наук: 13.00.02. Київ. ун-т ім. Бориса Грінченка. Київ, 2018. 262 с.
4. Пометун О. І. Сучасний урок. Інтерактивні технології навчання: наук.-метод. посібн. О. І. Пометун, Л. В. Пироженко та ін.; за ред. О. І. Пометун. К. Видавництво А.С.К., 2004. 192 с.
5. Словник-довідник з української лінгводидактики: навчальний посібник. Кол. авторів. За ред. М.І. Пентиліук. Київ, 2015. 320 с.

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A new word in English language teaching at schools and universities

The importance of finding the new creative approaches in English language teaching can't be doubted. Especially now, when Ukraine is building closer relations with most developed countries. The Russian invasion of Ukraine also increased the significance of learning English. Millions of refugees from our country found it difficult to live in unfamiliar cities where they had to communicate with local people either in English or other languages.

English is considered to be a global language, so it is easier for most people to master it and communicate with foreigners without any difficulties. Unfortunately, according to the recent survey only 1.1% of Ukrainians are fluent in English, and 43.8% of respondents do not know the language at all [1]. Another research shows that 23% of our people can read, write and communicate in English at regular or even professional levels [2]. According to these pieces of research it is clearly seen that Ukraine is one of Europe's worst countries at speaking English [3].

There are a lot of reasons for this:

- 1) English is different from Ukrainian language;
- 2) Ukrainians do not understand the importance of English;
- 3) Most people cannot force themselves to learn English because it is boring and complicated.

This article is focused on offering the new creative approaches in English language teaching at schools and universities to make this process easier and more pleasant.

Usually, when we're thinking about typical English lessons at school or university we can imagine a lot of grammar exercises, boring lectures and other unpleasant things. This is how it was in the USSR and the situation hasn't changed much. This approach is effective indeed. We can't doubt the general idea of learning grammar in this way. But the problem is that students won't be motivated and interested in attending such lessons. And this is crucially important nowadays – to get them interested and to persuade them to attend English lessons. Not because they'll receive bad marks if they don't, but because they are truly motivated to learn the language.

How to achieve this?

1. Don't be boring!

Firstly, an English teacher must become a real friend to his students. Being a teacher doesn't mean being serious all the time. It is sometimes possible to joke with students or discuss something interesting: a new movie, book, computer game or just latest news. Using English is essential of course. All these jokes and discussions must be in English.

2. Welcome to America! Speak English!

Secondly, it is extremely important to communicate with students in English all the time and everywhere: during lessons, in phone conversations, in messengers, in the shelter, on the street, in the corridors etc.

3. Watch this!

While communicating with students in messengers, it is a good idea to use some GIFs or short videos from different movies. This is one of the best ways to learn new words and phrases without straining yourself too much. Discussing these movies is a lot of fun too!

4. Aah! Not this again!

There are also a lot of creative ways to conduct lessons. An English teacher can use different locations to do this. Doing this in the same spot can be boring. It is possible to conduct an English lesson on the street, in the café, in the restaurant, in the supermarket, in the park, in the zoo, in the gym etc. Such lessons can help students to improve their speaking skills, get rid of language barrier and significantly expand their vocabulary. Learning new phrases is much easier when every word is connected with some unique memories and emotions.

5. Let's get this party started!

But changing locations is not a solution. The question is what those students are going to do there. Let's see. If it's a café, they can order food in English, communicate with each other, discussing different things. It will help them to get on well with each other, and improve their speaking skills, of course.

It is also possible to communicate with other students or pedestrians by asking them some questions.

Visiting different locations can help students to learn different specific words, connected to those places, for example: zoo – animals, gym – sport equipment, supermarket – products, café – food, etc.

So, what do we have in conclusion? We have an extremely effective methodology that can significantly increase students' motivation and make lessons more interesting. According to our observations, students start attending English lessons much more frequently and remember the material better. Also, they get rid of a language barrier and become more confident. Since they have more speaking practice, they make progress significantly faster.

Last but not least, students trust their teacher and respect him as a leader, not just because he's a teacher.

This is extremely important to implement these methods and develop them to teach English more effectively.

References

1. Bychenko A. MATRA Program Project Funded by the Embassy of the Kingdom of the Netherlands in Ukraine URL: <https://www.ukrinform.net/rubric-society/3740676-only-11-of-ukrainians-are-fluent-in-english.html>
2. Yashnyk M. Level of Proficiency in English and Other Foreign Languages in Ukraine: Results of Quantitative Sociological Research Conducted in December 2022 – January 2023. URL: <https://kiis.com.ua/?lang=eng&cat=reports&id=1210&t=10&page=1>
3. Sorokin O. Study: Ukraine one of Europe's worst countries at speaking English URL: <https://www.kyivpost.com/post/7356>